

The need for the rational expenditure of the resources and large-scale implementation of digital technologies for the society, require the transition to new principles of socio-economic sustainability, taking into account the emergence of the concept of a «smart city» and its use for the development of territories.

The article identifies the capabilities and factors of sustainable development of the territory based on «smart cities». The capabilities of the smart city are realized through six of its main components based on the use of ICT; called «smart»: economics; management; public; education, culture and health; mobility; urban environment. The socio-economic stability of the «smart city» determined by the following factors: first, adaptability including the use of digital platforms for managerial decisions. Second, network architecture participating in the creation of cyber-physical systems; integration meaning the unity of the goals of the development of urban territories; cooperation of all components of innovative sustainable development; creativity of all institutions; the ability to teach people and man-machine systems; analyzing data of large volumes coming from the Internet of things.

The author studied the concepts of the development of «smart cities» and their main provisions generalized. All concepts base on the main components of the Smart City, which complemented and detailed by various authors. The principles of the concept of «smart city» include: the use of ICT, the development of creative entrepreneurship, the development of the city community and the formation of social and human capital; training and development based on knowledge; Sustainable socio-economic development. In recent years, the concept of the Smart Garden has included the use of artificial intelligence systems.

The identified principles, components and factors of socio-economic stability and the development of «smart cities» formed the basis of the development of «smart territories», including urbanized territories and agro-industrial clusters that ensure their functioning.

In Russia, the federal project «Smart City» implemented, covering 209 cities with a population of 100 thousand people. An example of a specially built «smart garden» in Russia is Innopolis in the Republic of Tatarstan. Projects on the «smart specialization» of regions are also developing, for example, for the Republic of Crimea, this is recreation and tourism, for the Krasnoyarsk Territory — cooperation of large enterprises and scientific and educational institutions to create and promote innovative products. Thus, the global trend is the transition from the «smart garden» to the «smart region».

However, the costs of the formation and development of a «smart city» may be higher than expected, as their further payback. The article discusses the issues of individual projects of the Smart City based on foreign experience, financial aspects of sustainability.

The features of the sustainable socio-economic development of «smart cities» analyzed in the article allow you to develop strategies and business models of their further improvement, adoption of managerial decisions and differentiate these models for all aspects of the «smart city».

Keywords: Smart city, sustainable development, concept of a «smart city», the principles of sustainable development, digital technologies, region, cost of sustainable development, costs of the «smart city».

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